

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 6.4

Software framework for a shared agricultural soil information system

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Executive Summary

The deliverable "Software Framework for a Shared Agricultural Soil Information System" (D6.4) is part of the H2020 European Joint Research Programme EJP SOIL. It supports harmonized soil information and reporting by enabling the transcoding and streamlining of interoperable national agricultural soil data into the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC). This deliverable builds on the solid foundations of the INSPIRE Directive, taking advantage of the latest developments in the process of modernisation and simplification of its technical requirements in the wider context of the European Strategy for data and the Green Deal Data Space, enhancing data sharing and compliance.

This document is relevant for decision-makers, environmental managers, policy developers, and researchers engaged in soil data management and agricultural land use planning. It particularly targets those involved in implementing the INSPIRE Directive and managing soil-related datasets at the national and EU levels.

The [Good practice on GeoPackage encodings for INSPIRE data](#) introduced an INSPIRE data sharing mechanism that facilitates the production of data by data providers and its consumption by users. The deliverable builds on the GeoPackage encoding format as an alternative to GML for INSPIRE datasets. The deliverable "Software Framework for a Shared Agricultural Soil Information System" (D6.4) has been produced in the Geopackage format and is published in github: https://github.com/ejpsoil/inspire_soil_gpkg_template/tree/main.

It includes:

- a streamlined soil database in GeoPackage encoding format, developed following the INSPIRE Implementing Rules and Technical Guidelines, and the [Good practice on GeoPackage encodings for INSPIRE data](#) .
- a data transformation and harmonisation processes from Geopackage to GML format

[Four workshops](#) were organized (three in December 2024, and one in January 2025) and a tutorial manual was created, published in the github page, to disseminate knowledge and facilitate stakeholder engagement, and to guide users in importing and accessing soil data.

Key Results:

1. **GeoPackage Implementation:** A GeoPackage template was designed for the collection of soil data, based on the INSPIRE soil data model. The GeoPackage template is an SQLite database, that can store both vector and raster. It is lightweight, portable, and compatible across various environments (it can be used directly into GIS applications, such as QGIS), addressing connectivity and bandwidth limitations.
2. **Enhanced Data Accessibility:** The deliverable provides a user-friendly mechanism for Member States to publish INSPIRE-compliant soil data, fostering easier data exchange and use.

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3. Practical Support Tools: A tutorial manual and workshops facilitated the adoption of the framework, ensuring its accessibility for various stakeholders.

The deliverable represents a step forward in harmonizing soil data management across the EU. By leveraging the GeoPackage format, it simplifies data sharing and increases interoperability. The Geopackage format has already been adopted for other environmental data, such as for geology and air quality. The GeoPackage Soil template developed by EJPSOIL has been presented, after invitation by the European Environmental Agency, at the “Eionet TG Soil workshop 12 December 2024 online” as a tool which could be used by Member States to publish and exchange soil data in INSPIRE compliant format.

The findings directly support the Mission Soil objectives by improving data integration and accessibility. Policymakers are encouraged to adopt the GeoPackage framework for soil datasets, promoting uniform standards across Member States and enhancing decision-making processes related to soil management and sustainability, notably in the context of the future EU Soil Monitoring Directive.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
GML	Geography Markup Language
GPKG	Geopackage
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community ¹
IR	Implementing Rules
O&M	Observation and Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SQL	Structured Query Language
STA	Sensor Things API
UML	Unified Modeling Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

¹ We refer here to the acronym INSPIRE as defined by the legislation [Directive 2007/2/EC](#). For practice use INSPIRE is also meant as Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe.

1 EJP SOIL deliverable D6.4, Version1.1-RC

The following folders are included:

- docs
- geopackage
- halestudio
- postgis
- qgisstyle
- sql

1.1 docs folder

This folder contains the materials, presentations, and documents from the **EJP SOIL Workshops**, which focus on facilitating the encoding of soil data according to INSPIRE soil data specifications and UML structure. The workshops provide an introduction to the **INSPIRE-SOIL GeoPackage**, practical examples of its use, and advanced methods for data transformation and integration.

The workshops are available on YouTube at the following playlist:
[YouTube Playlist - EJP SOIL Workshops](#)

1.1.1 Presentations

The folder contains four PowerPoint presentations, each corresponding to one of the workshops:

1.1.1.1 Workshop #1- INSPIRE soil geopackage:

Title: A Good Practice to facilitate the encoding of soil data in accordance with the INSPIRE Soil Data Specifications

- **Description:**
 - Overview of the INSPIRE Soil UML model and the Observation and Measurement model, including their relevance for structuring soil data according to European regulations.
 - Presentation of the INSPIRE-SOIL GeoPackage as a good practice mechanism for soil data encoding and exchange.

1.1.1.2 *Workshop #2- INSPIRE soil geopackage:*

Title: Introduction to the INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage. Examples of practical usage for single data upload and data consultation, through QGIS.

- **Description:**
 - Practical examples of using the INSPIRE-SOIL GeoPackage for single data uploads and data consultation using QGIS.

1.1.1.3 *Workshop #3- INSPIRE soil geopackage:*

Title: Advanced use of the INSPIRE-SO Geopackage

- **Description:**
 - Demonstration of upgraded functionalities, including the creation of transformation projects for massive data uploads using Hale Studio software.

1.1.1.4 *Workshop #4- INSPIRE soil geopackage:*

Title: INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage implementation and extension, through the connection to existing registries of (soil) vocabularies (Codelists) and other basic principles of ontology.

- **Description:**
 - Introduction to connecting the GeoPackage to existing registries of soil vocabularies (Codelists) and basic ontology principles.

1.1.2 Additional Documents

The repository also includes the following documents that support the use and understanding of the INSPIRE-SOIL GeoPackage:

1.1.2.1 *GeoPackage Encoding Rules*

- **File:** EJP SOIL Encoding rules of the D6.4 Software framework for a shared agricultural soil information system.pdf
- **Description:** This document outlines the encoding rules of the GeoPackage as part of the D6.4 software framework for a shared agricultural soil information system. It provides guidance on structuring and encoding soil data following the INSPIRE Soil standards.

1.1.2.2 User Manual for QGIS

- **File:** INSPIRE SO Geopackage User Manual for compiling single features by means of QGIS.pdf
- **Description:** A user manual that demonstrates how to view and populate the INSPIRE-SOIL GeoPackage using customized forms in QGIS. It offers a step-by-step guide for compiling individual features with ease.

1.2 geopackage folder

The geopackage folder contains 4 subfolders, each one containing a different version of the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage file (INSPIRE_SO.gpkg). It provides resources for working with the INSPIRE Soil (SO) data model in GeoPackage format. Below is an overview of the folder structure and their respective contents.

Key Features are:

- INSPIRE Compliance

The GeoPackage files are designed to conform to the INSPIRE Soil data model, ensuring compatibility with EU standards.

- Ease of Use:

Pre-configured QGIS forms and project files simplify data management, visualization, and editing.

-- QGIS version 3.32.3-Lima or higher is required. --

- Sample Data:

Example datasets provide a practical demonstration of how to use the INSPIRE SO model effectively.

- Database Schema:

The schema diagram in `DB_Schema.png` visually explains the structure of the database.

Contents:

1. [DB_Schema.png](#)

Contents:

- A PNG file containing the database schema for the INSPIRE SO GeoPackage.

Purpose:

- To provide a visual representation of the database structure, helping users understand the relationships between tables and fields.

2. [`INSPIRE SO empty`](#)

Contents:

- A INSPIRE Soil Geopackage file (INSIRE_SO.gpkg) containing the complete INSPIRE SO data structure.

Purpose:

- To provide a clean template of the INSPIRE SO model for further customization and data population.

3. [`INSPIRE SO empty and QGIS project`](#)

Contents:

- A INSPIRE Soil Geopackage file (INSIRE_SO.gpkg) with the complete INSPIRE SO structure.
- A set of QGIS forms designed to assist users in:
 - Navigating the GeoPackage content.
 - Entering and managing data.

Usage Instructions:

1. Link the GeoPackage to QGIS.
2. Open the `**`SO_PRJ`**` project file (contained within the GeoPackage).
3. Use the provided forms for data management.

4. [`INSPIRE SO with data`](#)

Contents:

- A INSPIRE Soil Geopackage file (INSIRE_SO.gpkg) with:
 - The complete INSPIRE SO structure.
 - Sample data derived from the Soil Map of Sicily (scale 1:250,000) (Fantappiè et al., 2011²).

Purpose:

- To serve as an example dataset for testing and demonstration purposes.

² Fantappiè, M., Bocci, M., Paolanti, M., Perciabosco, M., Antinoro, C., Riveccio, R., et al. (2011). Realizzazione della carta digitale dei suoli della Sicilia utilizzando il rilevamento GIS-oriented e un modello CLORPT. In La percezione del suolo (pp.139-142). Le Penseur. (online) <https://iris.unipa.it/handle/10447/105053?mode=full>

5. [INSPIRE SO with data and QGIS project](#)

Contents:

- A INSPIRE Soil Geopackage file (INSIRE_SO.gpkg) with:
 - The complete INSPIRE SO structure.
 - Sample data derived from the Soil Map of Sicily (scale 1:250,000) (Fantappiè et al., 2011).
- A set of QGIS forms for:
 - Easier navigation of the dataset.
 - Data input and editing.

Usage Instructions:

1. Link the GeoPackage to QGIS.
2. Open the `**SO_PRJ**` project file (contained within the GeoPackage).
3. Utilize the included forms for efficient data handling.

1.3 halestudio folder

The halestudio folder contains:

- The [GPKG-to-GML.halez](#): A Hale Studio project for transforming the Geopackage file into a GML. This transformation to demonstrate INSPIRE compliance, Currently this can be demonstrated only using the INSPIRE Validator , which accepts only GML inputs.
- The [EJPSOIL Sicily.gml](#) and the [EJPSOIL Sicily_subset-2.gml](#): Resulting GML files after applying the project to the Geopackage located in the folder "geopackage\INSPIRE SO with data\INSPIRE_SO.gpkg".
- The [Test EJPSOIL with test suite Soil \(SO\).html](#). The successful report from the INSPIRE validator demonstrating the compliance with the INSPIRE soil model.

To convert the INSPIRE SO GeoPackage to GML using Hale Studio:

- download Hale Studio,
- download and open the [EJPSOIL-GPKG-to-GML.halez](#),
- select the INSPIRE SO GeoPackage populated with your data as source,
- run the transformation,

To demonstrate compliance, validate the resulting GML in the INSPIRE Validator
<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/validator/home/index.html>

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1.4 postgis folder

The postgis folder contains the [create_PostGis.sql](#) file, which contains SQL (DDL) code for defining a data model in PostgreSQL that mirrors the INSPIRE SO Geopackage structure. This script creates all necessary tables and populates the "codelist" table." The aim is to eventually provide users with a Server Side database that can simplify data exchange between the two Geopackage and the PostgreSQL formats.

The presence of Functions in the PostGis sql file, functionally corresponding to the Geopackage Triggers, ensures data integrity at the engine level. A full list of functions created is reported in the folder.

1.5 qgisstyle folder

The qgisstyle folder contains [QGIS](#) style files, which are customized forms to load for each individual table in QGIS. In this phase, we use this system for better form management. Later, the forms will be saved directly within the Geopackage.

1.6 sql folder

The `sql` folder contains the informatic code which is behind the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage.

Using the SQL code in the `create.sql` file, you can recreate the Geopackage containing the full INSPIRE Soil structure.

Recreating the Geopackage Containing the INSPIRE Soil Structure

These are the detailed instructions to recreate the Geopackage containing the full INSPIRE Soil structure.

1. Open the empty GeoPackage model available at <http://www.geopackage.org/data/empty.gpkg> using a database manager (e.g., DBeaver).
2. Execute the SQL instructions from the create.sql file in the query window.
 - The create.sql file includes:
 - **Data Definition Language (DDL):** Instructions to create tables and their relationships.
 - **Data Manipulation Language (DML):** Instructions to populate the codelist table with the necessary codelists required for its functionality.

- Some constraints have been managed through both form management and trigger creation, in order to:
 - assist user data entry.
 - ensure data integrity in case of massive data entry.

Create More Than One Geometric Layer Linked to the SoilBody Table

It is possible to create more than one geometric layer linked to the SoilBody table, to do this use the code provided in `SoilBody_newgeom.sql`.

Some names in the code need to be changed for it to work correctly, as described below.

1. SoilBody geometry table

- CREATE TABLE soilbody_newname ** CHANGE NAME **

2. gpkg_contents INSERT

- 'soilbody_newname', ** CHANGE NAME ** the name should be as entered in point 1
- 'f_sbsi', ** CHANGE NAME ID**
- 'soilbody_newname Table', ** CHANGE NAME DESCRIPTION OPTIONAL** the name should be as entered in point 1

3. Spatial index

- CREATE INDEX soiBody_geom_idxsi ON soilbody_newname(geom); ** CHANGE NAME INDEX ** AND ** CHANGE NAME AFTER ON ** the name should be as entered in point 1

4. gpkg_geometry_columns INSERT

- 'soilbody_newname', ** CHANGE NAME ** the name should be as entered in point 1

Trigger

A Trigger is a procedural code that is automatically executed in response to certain events, for maintaining the integrity of the information in the database.

Below is the list of triggers implemented for the INSPIRE SO data model, along with a brief description of their functionalities.

SOILSITE

- "soilsiteguid" - INSERT - manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "soilsiteguidupdate" - UPDATE - prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidperiodsoilsite" - INSERT - checks that the validfrom date should always be previous than or equal to validto
- "u_cekvalidperiodsoilsite" - UPDATE - checks that the validfrom date should always be previous than or equal to validto
- "i_cekvalidversionsoilsite" - INSERT - checks that beginlifespanversion should always be previous than or equal to endlifespanversion
- "i_soilinvestigationpurpose" - INSERT - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST soilinvestigationpurposevalue are entered in the "soilinvestigationpurpose" field
- "u_soilinvestigationpurpose" - UPDATE - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST soilinvestigationpurposevalue are entered in the "soilinvestigationpurpose" field
- "u_begin_today_soilsite" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating the table, beginlifespanversion is updated to today
- "u_begin_today_soilsite_error" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating, Endlifespanversion is after today

SOILPLOT

- "soilplotguid" - INSERT - manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "soilplotguidupdate" - UPDATE - prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidversionsoilplot" - INSERT - checks that the beginlifespanversion should always be previous than or equal to endlifespanversion
- "i_soilplottype" - INSERT - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST soilplottypevalue are entered in the "soilplottype" field
- "u_soilplottype" - UPDATE - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST soilplottypevalue are entered in the "soilplottype" field
- "u_begin_today_soilplot" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating the table, beginlifespanversion is updated to today
- "u_begin_today_soilplot_error" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating, Endlifespanversion is after today

SOILPROFILE

- "soilprofileguid" - INSERT - manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "soilprofileguidupdate" - UPDATE - prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidperiodsoilprofile" - INSERT - checks that the validfrom date should always be previous than or equal to validto.
- "u_cekvalidperiodsoilprofile" - UPDATE - checks that the validfrom date should always be previous than or equal to validto.
- "i_cekvalidversionsoilprofile" - INSERT - checks that the beginlifespanversion should always be previous than or equal to endlifespanversion
- "i_cekprofileLocation" - INSERT - checks that in the soilprofile table, in the case of a Derived profile, the foreign key for soilplot is NULL
- "u_cekprofileLocation" - UPDATE - checks that in the soilprofile table, in the case of a Derived profile, the foreign key for soilplot is NULL
- "i_cekprofileLocationobserved" - INSERT - checks that in the soilprofile table, in the case of an Observed profile, the foreign key for soilplot is NOT NULL
- "u_cekprofileLocationobserved" - UPDATE - checks that in the soilprofile table, in the case of an Observed profile, the foreign key for soilplot is NOT NULL
- "i_wrbreferencesoilgroup" - INSERT - check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbreferencesoilgroup" field
- "u_wrbreferencesoilgroup" - UPDATE - check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbreferencesoilgroup" field
- "u_begin_today_soilprofile" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating the table, beginlifespanversion is updated to today
- "u_begin_today_soilprofile_error" - UPDATE - checks that, upon updating, Endlifespanversion is after today
- "i_wrbproversion" - INSERT - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbversion are entered in the "wrbversion" field
- "u_wrbproversion" - UPDATE - checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbversion are entered in the "wrbversion" field

OTHERSOILNAMETYPE

- "i_soilname" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST othersoilnametypevalue are entered in the "soilname" field
- "u_soilname" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST othersoilnametypevalue are entered in the "soilname" field

ISDERIVEDFROM

- "i_checkisderived" - INSERT - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 1 because the value of the "base_id" field in the "isderivedfrom" table cannot be inserted because profile is not of type "derived".
- "u_checkisderived" - UPDATE - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 1 because the value of the "base_id" field in the "isderivedfrom" table cannot be inserted because profile is not of type "derived".
- "i_checkisobserved" - INSERT - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 0 because the value of the "related_id" field in the "isderivedfrom" table cannot be inserted because profile is not of type "observed"
- "u_checkisobserved" - UPDATE - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 0 because the value of the "related_id" field in the "isderivedfrom" table cannot be inserted because profile is not of type "observed"

SOILBODY

- "soilbodyguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "soilbodyguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidversionsoilbody" - INSERT - Checks that the beginlifespanversion should always be previous than or equal to endlifespanversion
- "u_begin_today_soilbody" - UPDATE - Checks that, upon updating the table, beginlifespanversion is updated to today
- "u_begin_today_soilbody_error" - UPDATE - Checks that, upon updating, Endlifespanversion is after today

DERIVEDPROFILEPRESENCEINSOLIBODY

- "i_ceklowervaluesum" - INSERT - Checks that the sum of "lowervalue" for a soilbody does not exceed 100%

- "u_ckecklowervaluesum" - UPDATE - Checks that the sum of "lowervalue" for a soilbody does not exceed 100%
- "i_checkisderived_soilbody" - INSERT - Checks that the soilprofile is of type Derived
- "u_checkisderived_soilbody" - UPDATE - Checks that the soilprofile is of type Derived

SOILDERIVEDOBJECT

- "soilderivedobjectguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "soilderivedobjectguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

ISBASEDONOBSERVEDSOILPROFILE

- "i_checkisobserved_dobj" - INSERT - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 1
- "u_checkisobserved_dobj" - UPDATE - Checks if the value of isderived in soilprofile is equal to 1

PROFILEELEMENT

- "profileelementguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "profileelementguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_ckeckvalidversionprofileelement" - INSERT - Checks that the beginlifespanversion should always be previous than or equal to endlifespanversion
- "i_ckeckvaliddeepprofileelement" - INSERT - Checks that the value of profileelementdepthrange_uppervalue is always less than the value of profileelementdepthrange_lowervalue
- "u_ckeckvaliddeepprofileelement" - UPDATE - Checks that the value of profileelementdepthrange_uppervalue is always less than the value of profileelementdepthrange_lowervalue
- "i_checkgeogenicfieldsnull" - INSERT - checks that if in the "layertype" field the value is different from "geogenic" the values in the "layerrocktype", "layergenesisprocess", "layergenesisenviroment" and "layergenesisprocesstate" fields are null
- "u_checkgeogenicfieldsnull" - INUPDATE - checks that if in the "layertype" field the value is different from "geogenic" the values in the "layerrocktype", "layergenesisprocess", "layergenesisenviroment" and "layergenesisprocesstate" fields are null

- "i_ceckhorizonfields" - INSERT - If we have a HORIZON, the values of the fields "layertype," "layerrocktype," "layergenesisprocess," "layergenesisenviroment," and "layergenesisprocesstate" must be NULL
- "u_ceckhorizonfields" - UPDATE - If we have a HORIZON, the values of the fields "layertype," "layerrocktype," "layergenesisprocess," "layergenesisenviroment," and "layergenesisprocesstate" must be NULL
- "i_layertype" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST layertypevalue are entered in the "layertype" field
- "u_layertype" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST layertypevalue are entered in the "layertype" field
- "i_layergenesisenviroment" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST eventenvironmentvalue are entered in the "layergenesisenviroment" field
- "u_layergenesisenviroment" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST eventenvironmentvalue are entered in the "layergenesisenviroment" field
- "i_layergenesisprocess" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST eventprocessvalue are entered in the "layergenesisprocess" field
- "u_layergenesisprocess" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST eventprocessvalue are entered in the "layergenesisprocess" field
- "i_layergenesisprocesstate" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST layergenesisprocesstatevalue are entered in the "layergenesisprocesstate" field
- "u_layergenesisprocesstate" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST layergenesisprocesstatevalue are entered in the "layergenesisprocesstate" field
- "i_layerrocktype" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST lithologyvalue are entered in the "layerrocktype" field
- "u_layerrocktype" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST lithologyvalue are entered in the "layerrocktype" field
- "i_check_depth_range" - INSERT - checks that at least one of profileelementdepthrange_uppervalue and profileelementdepthrange_lowervalue is not null.
- "u_check_depth_range" - UPDATE - checks that at least one of profileelementdepthrange_uppervalue and profileelementdepthrange_lowervalue is not null.
- "u_begin_today_profileelement" - UPDATE - Checks that, upon updating the table, beginlifespansversion is updated to today
- "u_begin_today_profileelement_error" - UPDATE - Checks that, upon updating, Endlifespansversion is after today

PARTICLESIZEFRACTIONTYPE

- "i_check_fraction_sum" - INSERT - checks that the sum of "fractioncontent" does not exceed 100.
- "u_check_fraction_sum" - UPDATE - checks that the sum of "fractioncontent" does not exceed 100.
- "i_check_particlesize_overlap" - INSERT - checks that the new range should not overlap or touch an existing range for the sameidprofileelement.
- "u_check_particlesize_overlap" - UPDATE - checks that the new range should not overlap or touch an existing range for the sameidprofileelement.

FAOHORIZONNOTATIONTYPE

- "i_ckeckfaoprofileelementtype" - INSERT - Checks that the profileelementtype is = 1, meaning that it is a HORIZON
- "u_ckeckfaoprofileelementtype" - UPDATE - Checks that the profileelementtype is = 1, meaning that it is a HORIZON
- "i_faohorizonmaster_1" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonmastervalue are entered in the "faohorizonmaster_1" field
- "u_faohorizonmaster_1" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonmastervalue are entered in the "faohorizonmaster_1" field
- "i_faohorizonmaster_2" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonmastervalue are entered in the "faohorizonmaster_2" field
- "u_faohorizonmaster_2" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonmastervalue are entered in the "faohorizonmaster_2" field
- "i_faohorizonsubordinate_1" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_1" field
- "u_faohorizonsubordinate_1" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_1" field
- "i_faohorizonsubordinate_2" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_2" field
- "u_faohorizonsubordinate_2" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_2" field

- "i_faohorizonsubordinate_3" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_3" field
- "u_faohorizonsubordinate_3" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faohorizonsubordinatevalue are entered in the "faohorizonsubordinate_3" field
- "i_faoprime" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faoprimevalue are entered in the "faoprime" field
- "u_faoprime" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST faoprimevalue are entered in the "faoprime" field

OTHERHORIZONNOTATIONTYPE

- "otherhorizonnotationtypeguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "otherhorizonnotationtypeguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_otherhorizonnotationtype" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST otherhorizonnotationtypevalue are entered in the "horizonnotation" field
- "u_otherhorizonnotationtype" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST otherhorizonnotationtypevalue are entered in the "horizonnotation" field
- "i_diagnostichorizon" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbdiagnostichorizon (in case OtherHorizonNotationTypeValue = "WRB") are entered in the "diagnostichorizon" field
- "u_diagnostichorizon" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbdiagnostichorizon (in case OtherHorizonNotationTypeValue = "WRB") are entered in the "diagnostichorizon" field

OTHERHORIZON_PROFILEELEMENT

- "i_ceckothprofileelementtype" - INSERT - Checks that in the profileelement table, the profileelementtype is = 0, meaning that it is an HORIZON
- "u_ceckothprofileelementtype" - UPDATE - Checks that in the profileelement table, the profileelementtype is = 0, meaning that it is an HORIZON

WRBQUALIFIERGROUPTYPE

- "wrbqualifiergrouptypeguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT

- "wrbqualifiergrouptypeguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_wrbqualifier" - INSERT - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbqualifier" field
- "u_wrbqualifier" - UPDATE - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbqualifier" field
- "i_qualifierplace" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbqualifierplacevalue are entered in the "qualifierplace" field
- "u_qualifierplace" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbqualifierplacevalue are entered in the "qualifierplace" field
- "i_wrbspecifier_1" - INSERT - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbspecifier_1" field
- "u_wrbspecifier_1" - UPDATE - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbspecifier_1" field
- "i_wrbspecifier_2" - INSERT - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbspecifier_2" field
- "u_wrbspecifier_2" - UPDATE - Check that only valid values from the CODELIST of the version selected in the wrbversion field are entered in the "wrbspecifier_2" field
- "i_wrbqualversion" - INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbversion are entered in the "wrbversion" field
- "u_wrbqualversion" - UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST wrbversion are entered in the "wrbversion" field
- "i_unique_wrbqualifiergrouptype" - INSERT - Check that there are no duplicate rows
- "u_unique_wrbqualifiergrouptype" - UPDATE - Check that there are no duplicate rows
- "i_check_specifiers_not_equal" - INSERT - Checks that wrbspecifier_1 and wrbspecifier_2 are not equal and that if wrbspecifier_2 is not NULL, wrbspecifier_1 must also not be NULL
- "u_check_specifiers_not_equal" - UPDATE - checks that wrbspecifier_1 and wrbspecifier_2 are not equal and that if wrbspecifier_2 is not NULL, wrbspecifier_1 must also not be NULL

WRBQUALIFIERGROUP_PROFILE

- "i_check_wrbversion_match" - INSERT - Check for each row that soilprofile and wrbqualifiergrouptype have the same version as WRB

- "u_check_wrbversion_match" - UPDATE - Check for each row that soilprofile and wrbqualifiergrouptype have the same version as WRB
- "i_check_qualifier_position_unique" - INSERT - Check if an idwrbqualifiergrouptype and qualifierposition record already exists for the same soilprofile
- "u_check_qualifier_position_unique" - UPDATE - Check if an idwrbqualifiergrouptype and qualifierposition record already exists for the same soilprofile

DATASTREAM

- "datastreamguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "datastreamguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_soilprofile_obspro" INSERT - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilprofile."
- "u_soilprofile_obspro" UPDATE - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilprofile."
- "i_soilsite_obspro" INSERT - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilsite."
- "u_soilsite_obspro" UPDATE - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilsite."
- "i_profileelement_obspro" INSERT - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "profileelement."
- "u_profileelement_obspro" UPDATE - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "profileelement."
- "i_soilderivedobject_obspro" INSERT - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilderivedobject."
- "u_soilderivedobject_obspro" UPDATE - Checks that in the "foi" field of the "observableproperty" defined by the inserted link, there is the value "soilderivedobject."

OBSERVATION

- "observationguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "observationguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidperiodobservation" INSERT - Checks that the result time is earlier than the valid time

- "u_cekvalidperiodobservation" UPDATE - Checks that the result time is earlier than the valid time
- "i_controlresultvalue" INSERT - Checks that the value is within the Min and Max of the domain specified in the properties.
- "u_controlresultvalue" UPDATE - Checks that the value is within the Min and Max of the domain specified in the properties.
- "i_check_result_value_uri" INSERT – Checks that only one of the fields "result_value" and "result_uri" is populated.
- "u_check_result_value_uri" UPDATE - Checks that only one of the fields "result_value" and "result_uri" is populated.

DATASTREAMCOLLECTION

- "datastreamcollectionguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "datastreamcollectionguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_cekvalidphetimedatastreamcollection" INSERT - Checks that the "beginphenomentime" field is earlier than the "endphenomentime" field
- "u_cekvalidphetimedatastreamcollection" UPDATE - Checks that the "beginphenomentime" field is earlier than the "endphenomentime" field
- "i_cekvalidrestimedatastreamcollectionINSERT" - Checks that the "beginresulttime" field is earlier than the "endresulttime" field
- "u_cekvalidrestimedatastreamcollectionUPDATE" - Checks that the "beginresulttime" field is earlier than the "endresulttime" field

UNITOFMEASURE

- "uomguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "uomguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

OBSERVABLEPROPERTY

- "observablepropertyguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "observablepropertyguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

- "i_foi" INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the FOIType are entered in the "foi" field, identifying which type of Feature Of Interest that particular ObservableProperty should be associated with.
- "u_foi" UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the FOIType are entered in the "foi" field, identifying which type of Feature Of Interest that particular ObservableProperty should be associated with.
- "i_phenomenonType" INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "PhenomenonType" are entered in the "phenomenontype" field.
- "u_phenomenonType" UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "PhenomenonType" are entered in the "phenomenontype" field.
- "i_basephenomenon" INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST are entered in the "basephenomenon" field, with respect to the values entered in the "foi" and "phenomenontype" fields. - "u_basephenomenon" UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST are entered in the "basephenomenon" field, with respect to the values entered in the "foi" and "phenomenontype" fields.
- "i_ceckdomain" INSERT - Checks that the "domain_max" field is always greater than the "domain_min" field.
- "u_ceckdomain" UPDATE - Checks that the "domain_max" field is always greater than the "domain_min" field.
- "i_ceckdomain_code" INSERT - Checks that in case the "domain_typeofvalue" field takes the value 'result_value', the value of the "domain_code" field is null.
- "u_ceckdomain_code" UPDATE - Checks that in case the "domain_typeofvalue" field takes the value 'result_value', the value of the "domain_code" field is null.
- "i_ceckdomain_value" INSERT - Checks that in case the "domain_typeofvalue" field takes the value result_uri, the values of the "domain_min" and "domain_max" fields are null.
- "u_ceckdomain_value" UPDATE - Checks that in case the "domain_typeofvalue" field takes the value result_uri, the values of the "domain_min" and "domain_max" fields are null.

SENSOR

- "sensorguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "sensorguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

THING

- "thingguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "thingguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

PROCESS

- "processguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "processguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

DOCUMENTCITATION

- "documentcitinguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "documentcitinguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE

PROCESSPARAMETER

- "i_name" INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "ProcessParameterNameValue" are entered in the "name" field.
- "u_name" UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "ProcessParameterNameValue" are entered in the "name" field.

RELATEDPARTY

- "relatedpartyguid" - INSERT - Manages the creation of the GUID in INSERT
- "relatedpartyguidupdate" - UPDATE - Prevents the modification of the GUID in UPDATE
- "i_role" INSERT - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "ResponsiblePartyRole" are entered in the "role" field.
- "u_role" UPDATE - Checks that only valid values from the CODELIST "ResponsiblePartyRole" are entered in the "role" field.

Codelist Table.

Codelists in the SO (Soil) INSPIRE domain are essential for ensuring a standardized representation of soil data across the European Union. They enable consistent classification and encoding of specific values (e.g., soil types, usage categories) across different languages and applications, ensuring interoperability and semantic integrity in environmental datasets.

Although the codelist table has no relationship with other tables, its presence is crucial for the correct data management and control. Although the codelist table has no relationship with other tables, its presence is crucial for the correct data management and control. It includes replicates of all SO domain valid codes extracted from the INSPIRE registry (<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/registry>). Essentially, if a coded value is in the table, it is supposed to be valid; if not, the code is to be considered as incorrect, and the relative value isn't stored.

The presence of the codelist table in the Geopackage allows forms for displaying dropdown lists, simplifying the data entry. However, up to now (01/2025), not all the mandatory items foreseen in the INSPIRE SOIL UML structure have been populated into the INSPIRE registry. For those mandatory items foreseen in the INSPIRE SOIL UML structure for which there is not yet a published codelist inside the INSPIRE registry, that is, for WRBdiagnostichorizon, ProcessParameterValue, WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue (2014), WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue (2022), WRBQualifierValue (2022), and WRBSpecifierValue (2022)), we made reference to other officially maintained controlled vocabularies by means of URI.

Moreover, internal codelists have also been added to the overmentioned table to manage forms more efficiently. INSPIRE registry

Below is a list of Features with their respective codelists:

FEATURE soilsite

SoilInvestigationPurposeValue

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/SoilInvestigationPurposeValue>

FEATURE soilplot

SoilPlotTypeValue CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/SoilPlotTypeValue>

FEATURE soilprofile

WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue (2006) CODELIST **INSPIRE**

<http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue>

WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue (2014) CODELIST AGROPORTAL

<https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/AGROVOC/>

WRBReferenceSoilGroupValue (2022) CODELIST ORBL-SOIL

<https://obrl-soil.github.io/wrbsoil2022/>

FEATURE othersoilnametype

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OtherSoilNameTypeValue

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/OtherSoilNameTypeValue>

FEATURE profileelement

LayerTypeValue CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/LayerTypeValue>

LithologyValue CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/LithologyValue>

EventProcessValue CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/EventProcessValue>

EventEnvironmentValue CODELIST **INSPIRE**

<http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/EventEnvironmentValue>

LayerGenesisProcessStateValue CODELIST **INSPIRE**

<http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/LayerGenesisProcessStateValue>

FEATURE faohorizonnotationtype

FAOHorizonMaster

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/FAOHorizonMasterValue>

FAOHorizonSubordinate

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/FAOHorizonSubordinateValue>

FAOPrime

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/FAOPrimeValue>

FEATURE otherhorizonnotationtype

WRBdiagnostichorizon

CODELIST ORBL <https://obrl-soil.github.io/wrbsoil2022/chapter-03.html#sec-diagh>

FEATURE wrbqualifiergrouptype

WRBQualifierPlaceValue

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/WRBQualifierPlaceValue>

WRBQualifierValue (2006)

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/WRBQualifierValue>

WRBQualifierValue (2022)

CODELIST ORBL-SOIL <https://obrl-soil.github.io/wrbsoil2022/>

WRBSpecifiers (2006)

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/WRBSpecifierValue> (Under review)

WRBSpecifierValue (2022)

CODELIST ORBL-SOIL <https://obrl-soil.github.io/wrbsoil2022/>

FEATURE processparameter

ProcessParameterNameValue

CODELIST AGROPRTAL - LOD <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/> - <https://lod.nal.usda.gov/>

FEATURE relatedparty

ResponsiblePartyRole

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/metadata-codelist/ResponsiblePartyRole>

PARAMETER

SoilSiteParameterNameValue **PARAMETER soilsite**

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/SoilSiteParameterNameValue>

SoilProfileParameterNameValue **PARAMETER soilprofile**

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/SoilProfileParameterNameValue>

SoilDerivedObjectParameterNameValue **PARAMETER soilderivedobject**

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/SoilDerivedObjectParameterNameValue>

ProfileElementParameterNameValue **PARAMETER profileelement**

CODELIST **INSPIRE** <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/codelist/ProfileElementParameterNameValue>

2 Workshops online, programme, contents, participants so far, and materials.

2.1 Promotion and inscriptions

The workshops have been published online on the EJPSOIL website <https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil/news-events-newsletters/item/artikel/default-a779b1c61c> and widely promoted through mailing lists of the EJPSOIL stakeholders network, that is, through the EJPSOIL national hub, that is, enlarging to possible interested participants not belonging to EJPSOIL partnership.

4 Online Workshops on the INSPIRE-soil Geopackage. First Workshop is November 25th.

TIME
Monday 25 November 2024, at 11:00 - 13:00
Add to calendar

LOCATION
Online

Register

By Lonnie Nielsen Storgaard

EJP SOIL SUPPORTING STANDARD AND INSPIRE COMPLIANT SOIL DATA EXCHANGE IN EUROPE.

4 **ONLINE** WORKSHOPS ON THE INSPIRE-SOIL GEOPACKAGE.

The participation to the 4 workshops is free, but a registration is needed to this link: <https://forms.gle/Pu9Mje6gFGfdJcGs5>

Figure 1 snapshot of the publishing page in the EJPSOIL website.

133 inscriptions have been received. 3 workshops have been held in December 2024, and one workshop in January 2025, to which participated respectively: 95 at the first, 85 at the second, 50 at the third, and 43 at the fourth.

In figure 2 is reported the distribution of inscribed to the workshops among European countries.

Figure 2 Distribution of inscribed to the workshops among European countries.

In figure 3 is reported the distribution of inscribed to the workshops respect to their profession.

Figure 3 Distribution of inscribed to the workshops respect to their profession.

2.2 The contents of the 4 workshops

All the materials of the workshops are published on GitHub https://github.com/ejpsoil/inspire_soil_gpkg_template/tree/main.

Here is reported a description of the contents of the 4 workshops, which are [published in the EJPSOIL youtube channel](#):

1. First workshop on 25th November 2024, 11.00 to 13.00 am, CET time zone.

Basic introduction on the INSPIRE soil UML model and Observation and Measurement model, as standards foreseen by the European regulation to be use for soil data exchange : that is, the basic principles and concept behind the structuring of soil data, following European regulation and the soil conceptual model behind. INSPIRE Good Practice mechanism and the EJPSOIL Good Practice for the provision of INSPIRE soil data in GeoPackage format: INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage.

It has been uploaded on EJPSOIL YouTube channel in 2 parts :

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPZNtmB4tlw>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UvmhL5qLm7M>

2. Second workshop on 2nd December 2024, 11.00 to 13.00 am, CET time zone.

Introduction to the INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage. Examples of practical usage for single data upload and data consultation, through QGIS. What you find inside the GitHub. Demonstration of the INSPIRE SOIL Geopackage through a DBMS (Database Management System). Introduction to the INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage. Examples of practical usage for single data upload and data consultation, through QGIS. QGIS – STYLES Custom Forms for QGIS (data entry/view). Demonstration of the INSPIRE SOIL Geopackage use with QGIS.

It has been uploaded on EJPSOIL YouTube channel in 2 parts :

https://youtu.be/QhjVemKQk2Q?si=qyqkKD_nigTtEEbZ

<https://youtu.be/ZmHOHdwnw8k?si=LBfwgqImqn6ROjsb>

3. Third workshop on 9th December 2024, 11.00 to 13.00 am, CET time zone.

4. The Particle Size Fraction of the soil profile element. Example of use of the INSPIRE SO Geopackage in DBMS, R, Python environments. Basic of hale studio. Upgraded use of the INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage, and the construction of transformation projects from other database structures for massive data upload through Hale studio software. Upload data in the INSPIRE SO : simple example using sample data from LUCAS.

It has been uploaded on EJPSOIL YouTube channel in 1 part :

<https://youtu.be/ZygFE3Ekrqo?si=PIVH9n1zgdY2fVej>

5. Forth workshop on 13th January 2025, 11.00 to 13.00 am, CET time zone.

INSPIRE-SOIL Geopackage implementation and extension, through the connection to existing registries of (soil) vocabularies (Codelists) and other basic principles of ontology.

It has been uploaded on EJPSOIL YouTube channel in 1 part :

<https://youtu.be/0VPD10XijY0?si=ZEmpB5pV66xnD1-v>

2.3 The engagement in the workshops, pooling results

At the end of the first and of the final workshops, interactive pools through Mentimeter have been lunched. The results are here reported.

2.3.1 Mentimeter results after the first workshop

Among the 95 who participated to the first workshop, 38 participated to the Mentimeter pool, among which 33 were belonging to EU MS countries, 5 to EU non-MS countries (fig. 4). The majority of the participants belonged to the research and academia (26), but other categories of stakeholders were also present : 5 public service staff, 2 students and 3 private companies (fig. 5). The level of knowledge of INSPIRE was medium to low, especially in relation to the technical guidance and implementation rules (fig. 6). The formats and/or standards for soil data storage and/or exchange adopted were mainly flat tables such as csv and Excel format (fig. 7). Some declared to use also DB formats such as postgresql, sql, oracle database. The Geopackage format itself was declared to be adopted by a relevant number of respondents. Shapefile and GeoJSON for vector data. Geotiff for raster data. Other standards adopted were Sensorthings api and sta. Some even declared to use word and pdf files ! The self evaluation on knowledge on soil science and informatics demonstrated a great variety of participants, but with a mean higher knowledge in soil science than in informatics (fig. 8). In relation to the clarity of the different sections of the workshop they were mainly on an in-between value, but the most unclear were the sections on Observation&Measurement standard and on provision of sensor-based observations (fig. 9). The majority of the respondent answered that they maybe will use the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage, but that they will understand that after the next workshops, or that it was difficult to judge after only the first workshop (fig. 10). Eight participant over 27 responded that the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage will enable and facilitated the standard data exchange for soil theme. Only one participant responded negatively. Most of the burning questions and suggestions (fig. 11) were answered at the following workshops. A summary of the suggestions is to have follow-up courses in person, in which the participant could try to use the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage with their own datasets. This is a suggestions that we hope to fulfil in future projects such as the ongoing Soilwise soil mission, in which CREA is involved.

Mentimeter

Where are you from?

16 33

Figure 4 The Distribution of participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool, among EU Member State countries and EU – non MS countries. Note: the 5 who answered Non EU – countries were instead EU – non MS countries.

Mentimeter

To which stakeholders category do you belong?

8 33

Figure 5 The Distribution of participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool, among different stakeholders categories.

Mentimeter

How much did you know about INSPIRE before the workshop?

Figure 6 Level of knowledge about INSPIRE among the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

In which format and/or standard do you store and/or exchange your soil data?

74 responses

Mentimeter

Figure 7 Formats and/or standards for soil data storage and/or exchange adopted by the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

Please scale how much you self-evaluate to know about soil science and informatics.

4 35

Figure 8 Self evaluation in the subjects of soil science and informatics of the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

Was it clear the session on ... ?

7 35

Figure 9 Evaluation of clarity of the first workshop by the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

After this first workshop, do you think that the INSPIRE SOIL-Geopackage will enable and or facilitate the standard soil data exchange?

Figure 10 Evaluation of the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage by the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

Please write down: burning questions, doubt, suggestions ...

Figure 11 Burning questions and suggestions for improvement by the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

2.3.2 Mentimeter results after the fourth and last workshop

Among the 41 who participated to the fourth workshop, 21 participated to the Mentimeter pool, among which 20 were belonging to EU MS countries, 1 to EU non-MS countries (fig. 12). The majority of the participants belonged to the research and academia (10), but other categories of stakeholders were also present : 4 public service staff, 2 private companies and 3 other (fig. 13). The programming language most known was python, followed by SQL and R. (fig. 14). Some declared to know and use also VBA, JAVA, HTML and vuejs. In relation to the clarity of the different sections of the workshop the whole sessions of the fourth workshop resulted to be above a mean value for clarity (fig. 15). The majority of the respondent (14 over 20) answered that the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage will enable and facilitated the standard data exchange for soil theme (fig. 16), and 6 answered that itw as still very difficult to judge and the need to test the INSPIRE Soil geopackage with their own data. A summary of the suggestions (fig. 17) is to have follow-up courses in person, in which the participant could try to use the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage with their own datasets. This is a suggestions that we hope to fulfil in future projects such as the ongoing Soilwise soil mission, in which CREA is involved. The question related to the integration of Sampling class of FROST-Server was answered during the workshop.

Mentimeter

Where are you from?

Figure 12 The Distribution of participants to the fourth workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool, among EU Member State countries and EU – non MS countries.

Mentimeter

To which stakeholders category do you belong?

Figure 13 The Distribution of participants to the fourth workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool, among different stakeholders categories.

Mentimeter

What programming language do you know/use?

34 responses

Mentimeter

Figure 14 Programming languages known/used by the participants to the fourth workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

Was it clear the session on ... ?

5 20

Figure 15 Evaluation of clarity of the fourth workshop by the participants to the first workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

Please write down: burning questions, doubt, suggestions ...

5 5

Figure 16 Burning questions and suggestions for improvement by the participants to the fourth workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

Mentimeter

After 2 workshops, do you think that the INSPIRE SOIL- Geopackage will enable and or facilitate the standard soil data exchange?

Figure 17 Evaluation of the INSPIRE Soil Geopackage by the participants to the fourth workshop, who participated to the Mentimeter pool.

